

INFLUENCE OF LECTURERS' YEARS OF EXPERIENCE ON THEIR' AWARENESS, READINESS AND UTILIZATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR EDUCATION IN A NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT Globally, Artificial intelligence (AI) has enabled lecturers to conduct research, assess student work, and deliver teaching in novel and innovative ways. However, factors might influence how lecturers use AI. Therefore, this study evaluated how lecturers' years of experience affected their awareness, readiness and use of AI in the classroom at a Nigerian university. The study employed a descriptive survey as its research design. The study's population consisted of the 903 lecturers at Federal University of Technology (FUT) Minna, and a sample of 271 lecturers was selected using the proportional stratified random sampling approach. A developed validated, pilot tested questionnaire was used to collect data. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. One-way analysis of variance was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05. The hypotheses were tested using one-way analysis of variance at 0.05. With $F(2,268) = 0.474$, $p = 0.623$, $p > 0.05$ and $F(2,268) = 0.889$, $p = 0.4123$, $p > 0.05$, the study found no significant difference in the mean answer of university lecturers' awareness and readiness of AI for education based on their years of experience. Furthermore, there was a significant difference in the mean answer of university lecturers on their use of AI for education depending on their years of experience, favouring those with less experience ($F(2,268) = 3.185$, $p = 0.043$, $p < 0.05$). The study recommended among others, that university administration should create useful policies for medium and highly experienced lecturers to use AI.

KEYWORDS: Awareness, Readiness, Utilization, Artificial Intelligence, Years of Experience

I. INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria's education system where students are subjected to the traditional approach of learning, AI technologies can assist learners with different learning styles around the world as it fosters personalized learning. Therefore, lecturers should take advantage of AI as it can motivate learners and lecturers to be involved in the learning and teaching process. It will also enable teachers to perform more tasks and activities without stress and also improve learning outcomes. With the use of AI, instructors can analyze students' needs in a class and recognize those who are slow in understanding the topics and provide timely remediation. If a student has some weaknesses in some areas or he/she fails to understand few topics, AI technology of machine vision using face surveillance

would capture the learner's face and showcase it to the lecturer for appropriate action to be taken by the lecturer to improve learning. In addition, games learning platforms powered by AI make lessons fun, motivate the learners and sustain the interest of the learners during instructional delivery. As a facilitator, the lecturer helps the student actively participate in order to get a knowledge of the material (Masaazi, 2015). Intelligent books, smart gadgets, online browsers, learning platforms, education apps, and tutoring systems are just a few examples of how artificial intelligence has been used into education. By using artificial intelligence in teaching and learning, students will have access to large volume of real, pertinent information that will empower them to take charge of their education, investigate pertinent learning resources, and develop their curiosity rather than merely being passive recipients of information from lecturers. Hence, it will improve both self-learning and active participation in the learning process. By providing lecturers and students with innovative and creative ways to teach and learn, assess, acquire skills, communicate, share, create, grade, analyse, and interact with learning materials, AI is vital for their academic success in this digital age. When AI is properly included and utilized to its full potential in instructional delivery, it will enhance informed citizenship and digital literacy in the digital age. AI has permeated every aspect of education through learning platforms, online browsers, educational applications, and intelligent books (Karsenti, 2019). By enabling innovative approaches to teaching, learning, grading, assessment, and research, artificial intelligence (AI) can improve educational activities' efficiency and provide access to a wealth of information. Lecturers have a lot of work to do, particularly in Nigerian universities with little technology and big class sizes with students of varying learning capacities.

Lecturers can employ artificially intelligent equipment, software, and applications as highly useful auxiliary tools (Pokrivcakova 2019). The majority of lecturers have not sufficiently used the resources at their disposal, despite the advantages of using AI to enhance the effectiveness and efficacy of the teaching and learning process, assessment, and professional development of lecturers (Thomas et al., 2024). Since lecturers are the ones who use these technologies for teaching, there may be obstacles to their use of AI, such as their years of experience. The number of years that lecturers have taught, conducted research, and participated in community service both inside and outside of the institution is referred to as their years of teaching experience. As a quality indicator, lecturers' years of experience are crucial for their awareness, readiness and use of AI. According to Gbadamosi (2013), lecturers who have taught for less than ten years are considered less experienced, and those who have taught for more than ten years are considered seasoned. Cruz-Cunha *et al.* (2011) and Etiubon *et al.* (2014) study affirmed that lecturers' awareness, self-efficacy, readiness and impact can improved by their experience. So, lecturing experience can influence their activities in carrying out their tasks. Studies have revealed that higher experienced teachers are not technology ready. Khurshid and Zahur (2013) and Nannim et al. (2018) study proved that experienced lecturers were more aware and use AI technologies in their tasks. Studies by Sivathaasan *et al.* (2013), Khurshid and Zahur (2013) and Nannim et al. (2018) study revealed that more experienced lecturers used AI technologies than the less experienced ones. Based on these inconclusive results, this study aimed to assess the impact of lecturers' years on experience on their awareness, readiness and use of artificial intelligence for education. Despite the many advantages of using AI in education, not all Nigerian university lecturers have fully incorporated AI in their activities. This could be because they are not well-informed about the intelligent devices, software systems, and applications (apps) that are available to ease their tasks (Nannim et al., 2018; Onah et al., 2020). The degree of AI integration in Nigerian higher education may be impacted by a number of factors such as lecturers' demographic factors or characteristics. Therefore, the need to assess the impact of lecturers' years of experience on their awareness, readiness and utilisation of AI for education lecturers' awareness,

II. RELATED WORKS

Al-Awidi and Aldhafeeri (2017) investigated how prepared Kuwaiti teachers were to adopt the digital curriculum. A semi-structured interview was done with 21 participants out of the 532 randomly selected instructors who completed the online survey. After reviewing the literature on the technological readiness survey, the researchers created the survey questions. The range of years of

experience for the teachers was as follows: less than five years, six to ten years, eleven to fifteen years, and sixteen years and more. According to their years of experience, the results showed a substantial difference in the overall preparedness of teachers, favouring those with less experience. This study was carried out on lecturers at a Nigerian university, whereas the prior study was carried out on teachers in Kuwaiti schools. Using i-Think Mind Maps, Husin et al. (2017) study used quantitative correlational research. A series of questions created by the researcher served as the study's data gathering tool. There were fifty-nine secondary school history instructors in the sample. The respondents' preparedness level was 61.16%, suggesting that they are somewhat prepared to use i-Think mind maps in secondary school instruction. Additionally, the results demonstrated a substantial difference in teacher preparedness between history instructors with fewer than 10 years of experience and those with more than 10 years, favouring the latter. This study was carried out on instructors from several areas of specialization at a Nigerian university, whereas the prior study was limited to history teachers in Setiu, Terengganu.

Nannim et al. (2018) study used an explanatory sequential design. The researcher created a questionnaire with eighteen items. A stratified random selection procedure was used to choose a sample of 433 professors. According to the survey, 66% of ATBU lecturers were aware of the ICT teaching resources that were accessible. The results also showed that lecturers with more than 25 years of teaching experience had somewhat higher mean evaluations on their understanding of the university's ICT resources than their peers with less years of teaching experience. FUT Minna lecturers were the respondents of this study, whereas lecturers from ATBU were the respondents of the previous study. Yushau and Nannim (2020) examined the extent lecturers in a Nigerian institution used ICT resources for instruction. A descriptive survey approach was used in the study. His study's finding revealed that 212 lecturers accounting for 49.0%, were aware of the use of ICT in the classroom. 11.9% of the lecturers used ICT, indicating a low level of ICT utilization. The results also indicated that instructors with greater experiences used ICT resources for instruction more frequently than those with less experience. This study research is on AI, whereas the previous study was on ICT resources. Ojo *et al.* (2023) examined lecturers' duration of lecturing practices on awareness, and readiness as well as challenges facing the utilization of Open Educational Resources (OERs) in Nigerian universities. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. Two universities (federal and state-owned) offering Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programmes in each of the federation's six (6) geographical zones, resulting in one thousand four hundred and eighty-five lecturers being selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. Using descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, and ANOVA inferential statistics, the collected data were examined. Finding of the study revealed that there were statistically significant differences in the lecturers' years of teaching experience in the extent of lecturers' awareness of OERs and willingness towards usage of OERs for teaching. This study research is on AI, whereas the previous study was on OERs.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research design according to Rahi (2017), is a deductive research methodology in which a developed questionnaire is used to strategically gather data. Federal University of Technology (FUT) Minna is the Nigerian university selected for this study. The study's population is all 903 lecturers at FUT Minna in Niger State (Information Technology Service, 2021). The sample size of the study was 271 lecturers. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to select 30 percent of the lecturers across the nine schools in FUT Minna. According to Gill *et al.* (2010) the sample size based on the required accuracy is 260 for a population of 800 and 274 for a population of 1000 based on 95% confidence level and a margin of error of 5. Two hundred and seventy-one lecturers were therefore deemed suitable for the study. Data was gathered using a researcher-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by four experts and a guidance counsellor from the Federal University of Technology Minna, validated the researcher's questionnaire to determine its appropriateness. Forty-five lecturers participated in a pilot study at the University of Abuja. To confirm the instrument's internal consistency, the data were statistically analyzed using the Cronbach Alpha

Correlation Formula. Namdeo and Rout (2016) define internal consistency as the degree to which each item in an instrument measures the same idea and how the elements in an instrument relate to one another. The various components of the test yielded reliability coefficients of 0.87, 0.80, and 0.82 for awareness, readiness, and artificial intelligence utilization, respectively. Cronbach alpha values above 0.70 are regarded as suggestive of good reliability when assessing an instrument's dependability (Taber, 2016). As a result, the tool was deemed suitable for gathering the required data. The following research questions were answered in this study:

- (a). Based on years of lecturing experience, do university lecturers' awareness of AI for education differ?
- (b). Based on their years of lecturing experience, do university lecturers' mean response about their readiness to use AI in education differ?
- (c). Based on their years of lecturing experience, do university lecturers' mean response about their utilisation of AI in education differ?

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO1: Based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean responses about their awareness of AI for education do not differ significantly;

HO2: Based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean response about their readiness to use AI in education does not differ significantly;

HO3: Based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean response about their utilization of AI in education does not differ significantly.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: Based on their years of experience, do university lecturers' mean responses about their awareness of AI for education differ?. Mean and Standard Deviation were used as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of university lecturers' mean responses about their awareness of AI for education based on their years of experience

Years of Lecturing Experience	N	\bar{X}	Std. Deviation
1-8 (low experience)	80	63.93	12.59
9-15 (medium experience)	111	65.26	12.20
16 & above (high experience)	80	63.64	12.67

From table 1, low experienced lecturers had a mean of 63.93 with standard deviation of 12.59, medium experienced lecturers had a mean of 65.26 with standard deviation of 12.20, while high experienced lecturers had a mean of 63.64 with standard deviation of 12.67. This shows that lecturers of medium experience had the highest mean rating than lecturers with low and high experience respectively on their awareness of AI in a Nigerian university.

Research Question Two: Based on their years of experience, do university lecturers' mean response about their readiness to use AI in education differ?. Mean and Standard Deviation were used as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of university lecturers' mean response about their readiness to use AI in education based on their years of experience

Years of Lecturing Experience	N	\bar{X}	Std. Deviation
1-8 (low experience)	80	78.10	11.38
9-15 (medium experience)	111	77.16	12.11
16 & above (high experience)	80	79.51	12.52

From table 2, low experienced lecturers had a mean of 78.10 with SD of 11.38, medium experienced lecturers had a mean of 77.16 with standard deviation of 12.11, while high experienced lecturers had

a mean of 79.51 with standard deviation of 12.52. This shows that high experienced lecturers had the highest mean than low and medium experienced lecturers respectively on their readiness to use AI in a Nigerian university.

Research Question Three: to what extent are AI used in education by university lecturers according to their years of experience?. Mean and Standard Deviation were used as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of university lecturers' mean response about their utilization of AI in education based on their years of experience

Years of Lecturing Experience	N	\bar{X}	Std. Deviation
1-8 (low experience)	80	49.06	18.36
9-15 (medium experience)	111	43.81	11.21
16 & above (high experience)	80	46.86	13.89

From table 3, low experienced lecturers had a mean of 49.06 with SD of 18.36, medium experienced lecturers had a mean of 43.81 with standard deviation of 11.21, while high experienced lecturers had a mean of 46.86 with standard deviation of 13.89 respectively. This shows that low experienced lecturers had the highest mean than high and medium experienced respectively based on their utilization of AI in a Nigerian university.

A. TESTING OF RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis One: Based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean responses about their awareness of AI for education do not differ significantly. In testing hypothesis one, using One-way ANOVA was employed as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: One-way ANOVA on University Lecturers' Level of Awareness of Artificial Intelligence based on their Years of Experience

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	146.856	2	73.428	0.474	0.623 ^{ns}
Within Groups	41557.461	268	155.065		
Total	41704.317	270			

NS: Not Significant at 0.05 ($p > 0.05$)

From table 4, $F_{(2,268)} = 0.474$, $p = 0.623$. The p-value is greater than the level of significance, hence hypothesis one was not rejected. This shows that based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean responses about their awareness of AI for education do not differ significantly in a Nigerian University.

Hypothesis Two: Based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean response about their readiness to use AI in education does not differ significantly. In testing hypothesis two, One-way ANOVA was employed as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: One-way ANOVA on University Lecturers' Readiness to use Artificial Intelligence for Education based on their Years of Experience

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	256.949	2	128.475	0.889	0.4123 ^{ns}
Within Groups	38730.269	268	144.516		
Total	38987.218	270			

NS: Not Significant at 0.05 ($p > 0.05$)

From table 5, $F_{(2,268)} = 0.889$, $p = 0.4123$. The p-value is greater than the level of significance, hence hypothesis eight was not rejected. This reveals that based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean response about their readiness to use AI in education does not differ significantly in a Nigerian University.

Hypothesis Three: Based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean response about their utilization of AI in education does not differ significantly. In testing hypothesis three, ANOVA was employed as presented in Table 6.

Table 6: One-way ANOVA on University Lecturers' Utilization of Artificial Intelligence for Education based on their Years of Experience

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1323.196	2	661.598	3.185	0.043*
Within Groups	55671.202	268	207.728		
Total	56994.399	270			

*: Significant at 0.05 ($p < 0.05$)

From Table 6, $F_{(2,268)} = 3.185$, $p = 0.043$. The p-value is less than the level of significance, hence hypothesis three was rejected. This shows that based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean response about their utilization of AI in education differs significantly in a Nigerian University. A Scheffe post hoc analysis was done to determine the direction of the difference among their years of experience as presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Scheffe Post hoc Analysis on University Lecturers' utilization of Artificial Intelligence based on their Years of Experience

(I) Years of Lecturing Experience	(J) Years of Lecturing Experience	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1-8 (low experienced)	9-15	5.252*	2.114	.040	.17	10.33
	16 & above	2.200	2.279	.706	-3.28	7.68
9-15 (medium experienced)	1-8	-5.252*	2.114	.040	-10.33	-.17
	16 & above	-3.052	2.114	.386	-8.13	2.03
16 & above (high experienced)	1-8	-2.200	2.279	.706	-7.68	3.28
	9-15	3.052	2.114	.386	-2.03	8.13

From the Scheffe post hoc analysis, multiple comparisons on university lecturers' utilization of Artificial Intelligence for education based on their years of experience revealed that there is a significant difference between low experienced lecturers and those with medium experience. There was no significant difference between low and high experienced lecturer and between medium and high experienced lecturers.

B. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of this study also revealed that based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean responses about their awareness of AI for education do not differ significantly in a Nigerian University. This result is consistent with that of Nannim et al. (2018), whose study found no significant difference in lecturers' awareness of available ICT facilities based on their years of lecturing experience. Similarly, research by Ipek et al. (2020) found no significant difference in lecturers' awareness level based on their teaching experience in Turkey. This finding, however, contradict that of Khurshid and Zahur (2013), who found that more experienced lecturers were aware of creative teaching techniques than less seasoned ones. Ojo *et al.* (2023) finding also revealed that

there were statistically significant differences in the lecturers' years of teaching experience in the extent of lecturers' awareness of OERs for teaching.

Finding of this study also showed that based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean response about their readiness to use AI in education does not differ significantly in a Nigerian University. This is consistent with the findings of Alrashidi's (2017) study, which found no significant difference between subject instructors' readiness to use e-learning based on their years of experiences. Also, Jwaifell's (2019) study revealed that according to experience, instructors' readiness to include augmented reality at the TPACK domains did not differ. This study contradicts the findings of Husin et al. (2017), who found that experienced history instructors with less than ten years of experience had significantly lower teacher readiness than those with more than ten years, favouring the more experienced ones. Also, Badri et al. (2014) study found that teachers with 1–10 years of work experience were the readiest to use technologies followed by those with 11–20, 21–30, and 31–40 years of experience. This suggests that the less experienced a teacher is, the more ready they are to use technologies. In the same vein, research by Al-Awidi and Aldhafeeri (2017) found that less experienced instructors in Kuwaiti schools were much more ready to use digital curricula than more experienced ones. Also, Ojo *et al.* (2023) finding revealed that there were statistically significant differences in the lecturers' years of teaching experience in the extent of lecturers' willingness towards usage of OERs.

Finally, another finding of the study showed that low experienced lecturers used AI for education than medium and high experienced lecturers in a Nigerian university. This finding agrees with that of Ohiwerei and Onimawo (2016), whose study found that lecturers with less years of experience were more likely to use ICT equipment than the more experienced. Also, Sivathaasan et al. (2013), who found that lecturers with 10–15 years of teaching experience used electronic information resources more frequently than other lecturers. According to Khurshid and Zahur's (2013) research, more experienced educators used creative teaching techniques than less experienced ones. In the same vein, Nannim et al. (2018) study revealed that more experienced instructors made more use of ICT resources for instruction than those with less experience. The finding also contradicts that of Mahdi and Al-Dera (2013), who found no significant difference in the use of ICT between instructors with more than ten years of experience and those with less than ten years. The usage of educational software and the number of years of teaching experience of instructors did not significantly differ, according to Niederhauser and Stoddart's (2001) findings. Furthermore, based on biology instructors' teaching experiences, Gbadamosi (2013) found no significant difference in the degree of use of innovative teaching technologies.

V. CONCLUSION

The degree of AI integration in Nigerian higher education may be impacted by a number of factors such as lecturers' demographic factors or characteristics. This study investigated how lecturers' years of experience affected their awareness, readiness and use of AI for education in a Nigerian university. The finding of the study revealed that based on years of experience, university lecturers' mean responses about their awareness and readiness of AI for education do not differ significantly. The study further revealed that based on their years of experience, university lecturers' mean response about their utilisation of AI in education differs significantly in a Nigerian University. From the finding of the study, some digital gaps exist among low, medium and high experience lecturers on utilisation of AI in education as low experienced university lecturers used AI for education than medium and high experienced lecturers. This could be attributed to the fact that low experience are tech-savvy and would use AI often. The study revealed that years of experience do not influence lecturers' awareness and readiness of AI. Further finding revealed that years of experience influence lecturers' use of AI for education. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made as follows: since, low experienced university lecturers used AI for education than medium and high experienced lecturers, university management should formulate useful policies for medium and highly experienced lecturers to use AI; University management should collaborate with experts

in ICT and education to develop 21st-century learners centred course materials with interactive elements to enhance lecturers use of AI. Another measure is that adequate training programmes should be organised for medium and high experienced lecturers to provide them with the technological know-how to use AI in all areas of educational realms.

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